

theoretical content in practice-oriented scenarios, with peer learning and immediate feedback playing central roles. The game is primarily aimed at bachelor's students of business administration who wish to refresh or deepen their knowledge of quality management. Through its interactive design and group discussions, a motivating learning atmosphere emerges that prepares players for real-world challenges.

Facts

Release date:	2019
Developer:	Siegfried Zürn
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–4 companies (players)
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	60–150 minutes, depending on the scenario
Languages:	German
Environment:	Laptop or PC with internet access
Material:	Game board, cards (question, action, and event cards), company controller, QM store
Price:	Free for public educational institutions (raw data for game elements)

Resonance & Criticism

Since its introduction in 2019, Ab durchs QM has been successfully used in various courses (foundational study programs at Esslingen University of Applied Sciences and part-time programs at Aalen University). Students report increased motivation and a better understanding of complex topics in quality management. The ability to identify knowledge gaps and close them through discussions with peers was particularly highlighted. Some participants, however, felt the competitive elements were challenging, especially in heterogeneous groups with varying levels of prior knowledge. Nevertheless, the overall reception is positive, and the game is seen as a valuable addition to traditional exam preparation. Empirical results showed improved exam performance (Zürn et al., 2019).

Game Principle & Process

Ab durchs QM places players in the role of companies competing for a demanding major contract in quality management. Each company begins with defined product and process quality values as well as an employee competence level, all displayed on an individual company controller. At the beginning, the group—in consultation with the instructor or game leader—chooses one of three scenarios that differ in number of rounds, target quality level, and game duration:

The short game runs for 8 rounds and takes about 60 minutes; the medium game uses 12 rounds and lasts around 120 minutes; and the long game extends to 16 rounds with a total duration of roughly 150 minutes.

In each round, players complete tasks, collect resources, and make strategic decisions. Dynamic events and a QM store offer additional challenges and opportunities. At the end of each round, players review the results using a peer-review process, and the company controllers are updated. This mutual evaluation with immediate feedback integrates collaborative learning and reflects the audit concept of quality management.

After the final round, an end event is resolved. The company (player) that reaches the required minimum quality level—or, in case of a tie, has the highest combined product, process, and competence level—wins. With more than 100 randomly combinable cards, each playthrough creates a new, realistic situation that fosters curiosity and competitive spirit.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

After the game, participants should be able to use key QM tools (e.g., Ishikawa diagrams, House of Quality, control charts) effectively to assess and initiate quality and process improvements in a simulated business environment. Through repeated decision-making under time pressure, they train their competence in knowledge transfer—also relevant for exam questions—by translating theoretical models into concrete actions. The competitive character challenges them to conduct critical analyses and assess the short- and long-term effects of their decisions. Simultaneously, the peer-review phase strengthens communication and teamwork skills, as learners provide feedback and justify potential improvements.

Learning objectives are achieved as follows within the game: Specific knowledge is applied through technical terms and indicators on the cards, enabling learners to translate theory into language and decisions immediately. By acquiring and applying QM methods from the QM store, the transfer of competence of theoretical concepts into operational measures is strengthened. Event cards create goal conflicts (cost vs. quality), requiring option evaluation and critical thinking. The collaborative processing of main events and mutual audits anchors collaborative problem-solving and promotes teamwork.

The game is suitable for exam preparation in quality management courses, knowledge refreshers in workshops, and application in part-time study programs.

Effectiveness

Comparative studies showed that participants who used *Ab durchs QM* achieved, on average, 0.3 to 0.6 grade levels higher results than those who prepared traditionally for the same exam (Zürn et al., 2019). Participants emphasized the strong learning effect resulting from the combination of fun, competition, and direct feedback.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Different levels of prior knowledge within a group can affect the dynamics. When prior knowledge varies significantly, some players may feel over- or underchallenged. The competitive drive may discourage players with lower levels of previous knowledge. However, a cooperative mode (teams working together against a fictional competitor) or bonus points for constructive peer feedback can help mitigate this.

The physical game material is designed for up to 4 players. When multiple groups play in parallel, the facilitation becomes increasingly complex, making it advisable for larger groups to use rotating player roles (observer and player). Setting up the game board and learning the rules takes about 15–20 minutes, which must be factored into tight seminar schedules. Learning success strongly depends on the instructor or game leader who explains the rules, stimulates discussion, and asks transfer-oriented questions.

Reviewer(s): Christian A. Zimmermann

Sources

Zürn, S., Bekolli, S., Pawelek, R. P., Ruffnen, C., & Kloss, D. (2019). Ein Qualitätler spielt nicht! – oder doch? Entwicklung und Einsatz eines von Studierenden entwickelten Planspiels für die Lehre im Qualitätsmanagement. In T. Alf, C. Hühn, B. Zürn, & F. Trautwein (Eds.), *Planspiele – anders denken: Kreative Ansätze, gelebte Wissenschaft* (ZMS-Schriftenreihe, Vol. 12, pp. 91–102). Zentrum für Managementsimulation.